

D5.3

Update scalable and adjustable documentation of how to understand the aggregators' technical requirements

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Abstract	Deliverable D5.3 of the CRAFT-OA Horizon Europe project describes the framework used to produce, maintain, and enrich the <i>Guide to Scholarly Indexes</i> , a document about the requirements of scholarly publications indexes.

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List of Acronyms

AMU	Aix-Marseille Université
API	Application Programming Interface
BASE	Bielefeld Academic Search Engine
CEEOL	Central and Eastern European Online Library
CORE	Connecting Repositories
CPU	Central Processing Unit
DIAMAS	Developing Institutional Open Access Publishing Models to Advance Scholarly Communication
DISCO	Discovery Companion (OJS plugin)
DOA	Diamond Open Access
DoA	Description of Action
DOAJ	Directory of Open Access Journals
FTE	Full Time Equivalent
EDCH	European Diamond Discovery Hub
.gdoc	Google Document (file format)
GDrive	Google Drive

HTML	Hypertext Markup Language
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation (text file format)
KB	Knowledge Base
KER	Key Exploitable Result
OJS	Open Journal System
OPERAS	Open Access in the European Area through Scholarly Communication
OpenAIRE	Open Access Infrastructure for Research in Europe
PDF	Portable Document Format
PID	Persistent Identifier
PHP	Hypertext Preprocessor
TF	Task Force
URL	Uniform Resource Locator
WP	Work Package
XML	Extensible Markup Language

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1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document constitutes a new and complementary version of the T5.1 deliverable: “CRAFT-OA Deliverable 5.1 Scalable and Adjustable Documentation on How to Understand the Aggregators' Technical Requirements”. The objective of the task is to provide Diamond Open Access (DOA) publishers with detailed documentation about the requirements of scholarly publication indexes and aggregators. The set of final outputs of the task forms what is globally called the *Guide to Scholarly Indexes* and corresponds to the project Key Exploitable Result (KER) number 6. The *Guide to Scholarly Indexes* includes the internal and the public versions of the Knowledge Base (KB) and the Catalogue.

The deliverable D5.1 contains concept definitions, design options and prototypes of the *Guide to Scholarly Indexes*. This deliverable, D5.3, describes the framework used to produce, maintain, enrich, and develop the *Guide to Scholarly Indexes*. With respect to D5.1, D5.3 presents substantial evolutions in terms of workflow, terminology, and outputs. The framework precisely captures these evolutions. The document can be thought of as an instruction pamphlet and therefore it describes key processes in the generation and maintenance of the KB.

The introduction explains the purpose and the structure of the document: the sections follow in a linear fashion the generation process of the index descriptions. It also provides definitions for the main concepts and terms used, as well as a table containing all the links to the files produced.

The first step of the process consists in populating the KB. The KB is a structured spreadsheet using a template to collect information about scholarly indexes in a consistent way. The template contains guidelines to ensure that any operator collects the information in the same way. The KB exists in two versions: an internal version containing all the work in progress, and a public version containing the validated entries. The KB information is then used to produce a more user-friendly version called “Catalogue” on a GitHub repository. The document finally lists all the access points to the various components of the *Guide to Scholarly Indexes* produced throughout the process.

The last sections discuss the sustainability aspects, with options for collecting feedback and suggestions from the community. Longer term sustainability is also described in the specific context of the European Diamond Capacity Hub (EDCH).

2 INTRODUCTION

2.1 Purpose and structure of this document

This document constitutes a new and complementary version of the T5.1 deliverable: “CRAFT-OA Deliverable 5.1 Scalable and Adjustable Documentation on How to Understand the Aggregators' Technical Requirements”¹. The objective of the task is to provide Diamond Open Access (DOA) publishers with detailed documentation about the requirements of different scholarly publication indexes and aggregators. The set of final outputs of this task forms what is globally called the *Guide to Scholarly Indexes* and corresponds to the project Key Exploitable Result (KER) number 6. The *Guide to Scholarly Indexes* includes the internal and the public versions of the Knowledge Base (KB) and the Catalogue.

The deliverable D5.1 contains concept definitions, design options and prototypes of the *Guide to Scholarly Indexes*. This deliverable, D5.3, describes the framework used to produce, maintain, and enrich the *Guide to Scholarly Indexes*. It describes the extensive and practical methodology used to create the planned “scalable and adjustable documentation” on scholarly indexes, as well as the final and fully public state of such documentation. The framework is meant to ensure the future development and maintenance of the *Guide to Scholarly Indexes*. Therefore D5.3 also includes considerations about the potential developments and sustainability options.

The framework reproduces, in a linear fashion, the various steps to produce and provide to the DOA community a catalogue of documentation about different indexes for scholarly publications. Although created in the context of CRAFT-OA, the *Guide to Scholarly Indexes* describes indexes that are not all exclusively dedicated to DOA.

The framework is divided into three successive stages:

- The “KB information collection” is an internal process that relies on populating the KB following a template and its guidance.
- The “Catalogue entry generation” aims to produce files for storage on a GitHub repository and ensures consistency between KB and the GitHub Markdown files.
- The last step “Access to the KB and Catalogue” addresses the public dissemination of the outputs, either by adapting some files or by identifying specific dissemination channels.

The section “[Knowledge Base: Information Collection](#)” describes the steps and tools to collect and organize the information about the various services that index scholarly publications. The

¹ Gingold, A., & Cuel-Oller, N. (2024). CRAFT-OA Deliverable 5.1 Scalable and Adjustable Documentation of How to Understand the Aggregators' Technical Requirements (Draft). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12634606>

second section, "[Catalogue entry generation](#)" explains how the public files are generated from the KB. The third section, "[Access points to the KB and the Catalogue](#)" lists all the access points to the catalogue, for consultation or potential feedback.

A dedicated section then describes how the community can provide feedback on the documentation. The last section gives a few hints about how the KB and its various expressions can be supported over time in the context of the European Diamond Capacity Hub (EDCH) building.

2.2 Terms and concepts used in this document

Below is an explanation of the usage of certain terms and concepts in the specific context of this work.

Index: In this document, "index" refers to any service operating in the academic publishing area and effectively indexing publications or journals, whatever the means and forms of such indexing. Although typology and appellations can vary a lot (from aggregators, to catalogues, or databases, etc.), the simple operation of indexing can be considered a common minimal characteristic of all these services.

Documentation: In this document, "documentation" refers to the contents collected and gathered in the outputs (KB and Catalogue). It does not refer to the documentation provided by the indexes themselves, which are only linked to in the KB and the Catalogue.

Knowledge Base (KB): The KB is the main place where all information related to the indexes is recorded in a structured way. It consists of a single spreadsheet file containing tables for each index (currently stored on Google Drive). The KB exists in two versions: an internal working file with validated and pending documentation; and a public final file with only the validated documentation.

Catalogue: The Catalogue refers to a set of single files (in Markdown format) containing the documentation of each index. The Catalogue duplicates the contents of the KB with only a few format adjustments. Like the KB, the Catalogue exists in two versions: in a private GitHub repository for editing and in a public GitHub repository for consultation.

Entry: In both the KB and the Catalogue, 'Entry' refers to the documentation for each single index. For example, ERIH PLUS corresponds to one entry in the KB (a specific tab in the spreadsheet) and one entry in the Catalogue (a specific file on the repository).

Entry field: "Entry field" corresponds to each unit of information that together constitutes the index documentation. For example, "Name", "Index sources", and "Joining options" are all entry fields of the KB or the Catalogue.

2.3 Framework outline

As mentioned above, the framework divides the documentation catalogue generation into distinct steps, each corresponding to a specific file. It also includes the outputs available to the public.

Here are the steps and their corresponding working or output files. Links to all the files mentioned in the list below are available in [the next section](#):

- KB information collection (limited access files):
 - Starts in the file “IndexesKnowledgeBase-FOLLOW-UP”,
 - Follows a template which contains indications about each field (available in the same file),
 - Applies a controlled vocabulary for the service’s type and the missing information (available in the same file).
- Catalogue entry generation (limited access files):
 - Follows a Google document template partially reproducing the KB template structure,
 - Generates a Markdown file for upload to a private GitHub repository,
 - Ensures consistency between the KB (spreadsheet) and Catalogue (GitHub) entries.
- Access to the KB and Catalogue (open files):
 - Provides a filtering tool called “Index Search Matrix” allowing to pre-select useful indexes,
 - Adapts the KB internal file to provide a public version called “IndexesKnowledgeBase-VALIDATED”, available at least on Google Drive,
 - Makes the full Catalogue available on a public GitHub repository (Open Access in the European Area through Scholarly Communication (OPERAS) repository),
 - Records the public GitHub repository in the CRAFT-OA Discovery Companion (DISCO) plugin.

2.4 Summary table

The table below provides the links to all the documents of the framework mentioned above. The documents that are publicly available are tagged as OPEN. All the others, marked as LIMITED, are accessible only to the CRAFT-OA project team or to the persons involved in managing the documentation catalogue.

Files	Link	Access
Information collection		
KB follow-up file (internal)	https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1hg2evNSaylQLgxS4NionMa27bKpDKKNQrD-4cak6gp0/edit?gid=571401641#gid=571401641	LIMITED
Catalogue entry template (tab in the KB)	https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1hg2evNSaylQLgxS4NionMa27bKpDKKNQrD-4cak6gp0/edit?gid=52626720#gid=52626720	LIMITED
Index service types (tab in the KB)	https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1hg2evNSaylQLgxS4NionMa27bKpDKKNQrD-4cak6gp0/edit?gid=1553214763#gid=1553214763	LIMITED
Catalogue entry generation		
Entry model for GitHub	https://docs.google.com/document/d/1mqp_ijbviTJgoFMtf1vMjjOwhbKaxaPLg6BbP2UFg-0/edit?tab=t.0#heading=h.s8hjpt7b301h	LIMITED
Generation of files for GitHub from the KB entries	https://docs.google.com/document/d/1U4JeqSIOEvOLUJYgj70HrRm-Hpn_b4IkQdQ8aY3DFlg/edit?tab=t.0	LIMITED
KB/ Google Document (Gdoc)/GitHub alignment method	https://docs.google.com/document/d/1KoG-84Vqb5UNB5YbNnIndexDocumentation-AlignmentMethod-V2OOIRK3x7vLBWO2l7aNMSpxdN4/edit?tab=t.0#heading=h.2uca75h08opd	LIMITED
Access to the KB/catalogue		
Indexes matrix (search filters)	https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/17l6X3P8lynO4k-lq4gJ7uBvBEIvoZ_yFFx37tyxd8x0/edit?gid=198817	LIMITED

	5915#gid=1988175915	
KB validated file on Google Drive (GDrive)	https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1N_tpg_MblDbxinkOyhzT9xtKIK5wpf82AFPrV5VH7IFA/edit?gid=571401641#gid=571401641	OPEN
KB validated file on Zenodo	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15600155	OPEN
Public official release on GitHub	https://github.com/operas-eu/craft-oa-ScholIndexes-doc/tree/main	OPEN
Catalogue integrated in Open Journal System (OJS) DISCO plugin	https://github.com/munipress/disco/tree/ojs-3-2-0	OPEN

Table 1: Hyperlinks to internal and public files of the KB and the Catalogue

3 KNOWLEDGE BASE: INFORMATION COLLECTION

3.1 Content files

3.1.1 KB follow-up file

The information about academic publishing indexes is recorded in a Google spreadsheet accessible only to the project partners, called "IndexesKnowledgeBase-FOLLOW-UP"². This file is used to collectively update information about indexes and serves as a tool to monitor updates until their final validation.

3.1.1.1 'MONITORING' TAB

This first tab of the spreadsheet contains columns tracking the KB updates status, as well as columns with general information about the indexes.

Creating the documentation typically follows these steps: information collection, 1st review, 2nd review, validation, and publishing on GitHub. The monitoring tab records the primary author of a KB entry, the review status, the final validation, and whether or not the entry is published on GitHub. The information columns (object types, geographic area, etc.) are not necessary for this collection/review/validation process. However, these columns are used in the public version of the KB, and copy-pasted from this file.

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J
	Priority (1 to 3)	Primary author	Done	Version	Checked	Validated	On Github	Name	Service URL	CF
2		AG	x	3	x	x	x	BASE	https://www.base-search.net/	htt
3			x	3	x	x	x	CEEOL	https://www.ceeol.com/	htt
4			x	3	x	x	x	CORE	https://core.ac.uk/	htt
5		NCO	x	3	AG	x	x	Crossref	https://www.crossref.org/	htt
6			x	3	NCO/AG	x	x	Datacite	https://datacite.org/	htt
7			x	3	NCO/AG	x	x	Dimensions	https://www.dimensions.ai/	htt
8			x	3	x	x	x	DOAJ	https://doaj.org/	htt
9			x	3	NCO/AG	x	x	EBSCO	https://www.ebsco.com/	htt
10			x	3	x	x	x	ERIH+	https://kanalregister.hkdir.no/publis	htt
11		AG	x	3	x	x	x	Google Scholar	https://scholar.google.com/	htt
12			x	3	x	x	x	GoTriple	https://www.gotriple.eu/	htt
13			x	3	x	x	x	OpenAIRE	https://explore.openaire.eu	htt
14		AG	x	3	x	x	x	OpenAlex	https://ourresearch.org/	htt
15			x	3	x	x	x	PubMed	https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/	htt
16			x	3	x	x	x	Scopus	https://www.elsevier.com/	htt
17		NCO	x	3	AG	x	x	Semantic Scholar	https://www.semanticscholar.org/	htt
18			x	3	x	x	x	WoS	https://clarivate.com/	htt
19	2		x	3	NCO			EZB	https://ezb.ur.de/	
20	1	NCO	x	3	AG			Latindex	https://latindex.org/latindex/	

Figure 1: Monitoring tab in KB follow-up file

² <https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1hg2evNSaylQLgxS4NionMa27bKpDKKNQrD-4cak6gp0/edit?gid=571401641#gid=571401641>

3.1.1.2 INDEX DOCUMENTATION TAB

The documentation for each index corresponds to one tab. New tabs are progressively added after each review and validation. All documentation follows the same template (see “[Content structure](#)” below).

	A	B
1		
2	Summary	ERIH PLUS is an online index holding bibliographic information on access in the Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH), with a focus on quality journals in all European languages and countries. ERIH PLUS supports journals' openness and transparency in line with editorial best practices. Curatorial journals open access status and Plan S compliance is marked. ERIH PLUS is an additional index of articles, which is an SSH subset of Dimensions collection showing only articles having a DOI. Dimensions is a multidisciplinary database that brings together over 140 million publications.
3	SERVICE DESCRIPTION	
4	Name	ERIH PLUS
5	Website	https://kanalregister.hkdir.no/publiseringsskanaler/erihplus/
6	Owner	Norwegian Ministry of Education and Research
7	Owner type	Public research organization
8	Owner country	Norway
	Launch year	2014

Figure 2: Extract from an index entry in the KB

3.1.1.3 SOURCES AND NOTES COLUMNS

The entry for each index in the KB FOLLOW-UP file also contains two columns for recording the documentation generation process: “SOURCE” and “NOTES”.

“SOURCE” is used to ensure transparency of the information and to facilitate both review and updating of the KB. It contains the Uniform Resource Locators (URLs) from where the information has been collected, and whether it has been copied or adapted. Not all the fields receive a provenance URL; only those that contain complex information or require regular updates.

“NOTES” is used for the review process to track down missing, inaccurate, or unclear information. The reviewers use it as a chat box. This option is preferred over the built-in Google comments, as those are hidden by default and are not easy to track. They also offer limited space. For “NOTES”, the best practice is to include the initials of the note's author and potentially the date.

The “SOURCE” column is kept for the KB public version, as it ensures information transparency for the end user. The “NOTES” column, on the contrary, is available only in the FOLLOW-UP file. Neither “SOURCE” nor “NOTES” appears on the catalogue (GitHub repository).

	A	B	C	D
1	Summary	ERIH PLUS is an online index holding bibliographic information on academic journals in the Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH), with a focus on quality journals across all European languages and countries. ERIH PLUS supports journals' policies of openness and transparency in line with editorial best practices. Curation ensures that journals open access status and Plan S compliance is marked. ERIH PLUS offers an additional index of articles, which is an SSH subset of Dimensions collections, showing only articles having a DOI. Dimensions is a multidisciplinary database that brings together over 140 million publications.	SOURCE (NOT IN DOC) https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/ERIH_PLUS	NOTES (NOT IN DOC/NOT IN PUBLIC KB)

Figure 3: Extract from an index entry in the KB with the SOURCES and NOTES columns

3.1.2 KB validated file

Once full reviewed and validated, the indexes' documentation is transferred to a publicly accessible Google spreadsheet, called "IndexesKnowledgeBase-VALIDATED"³.

This file, like the internal KB file, contains relative links to the index tabs and a link to the GitHub repository. The only difference is that the GitHub link points to the OPERAS repository and not to the private GitHub repository used for the validation process.

	A	B	C
1	Name	Service URL	CRAFT-OA index catalog URL
2	BASE	https://www.base-search.net/	https://github.com/operas-eu/craft-oa-5
3	CEEOL	https://www.ceeol.com/	https://github.com/operas-eu/craft-oa-5
4	CORE	https://core.ac.uk/	https://github.com/operas-eu/craft-oa-5
5	Crossref	https://www.crossref.org/	https://github.com/operas-eu/craft-oa-5
6	Datacite	https://datacite.org/	https://github.com/operas-eu/craft-oa-5
7	Dimensions	https://app.dimensions.ai/discover/publication	https://github.com/operas-eu/craft-oa-5
8	DOAJ	https://doaj.org/	https://github.com/operas-eu/craft-oa-5
9	EBSCO	https://www.ebsco.com/	https://github.com/operas-eu/craft-oa-5
10	ERIH+	https://kanalregister.hkdir.no/publiseringskanal	add when final url ready
11	Google Scholar	https://scholar.google.com/	add when final url ready
12	GoTriple	https://www.gotriple.eu/	add when final url ready
13	OpenAIRE	https://explore.openaire.eu	add when final url ready
14	OpenAlex	https://ourresearch.org/	add when final url ready
15	PubMed	https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/	add when final url ready
16	Scopus	https://www.elsevier.com/	add when final url ready
17	Semantic Scholar	https://www.semanticscholar.org/	add when final url ready
18	WoS	https://clarivate.com/	add when final url ready

Figure 4: Validated KB first tab

3

https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1N_tpgMbldbxinkOyhzT9xtKIK5wpf82AFPrV5VH7IFA/edit?gid=571401641#gid=571401641

3.2 Content structure

3.2.1 Template

The template contains fields in a flat structure, introduced by a summary about the index described. Each entry field in the template includes an explanation of the expected content type (see Annex 10.1).

Here are the template's top-level blocks of information:

- Service description: contains general, administrative, and typology information about the index;
- Service provision: contains information about the service delivery, like types of content handled, standards supported, and user support provided;
- Inclusion process: contains information on the modality of contents inclusion and the data collection process;
- Minimum requirements: contains a description of the mandatory criteria of inclusion, either on the editorial or technical side;
- Additional criteria: contains a description of the non-mandatory criteria that the index suggests to respect;
- Information sources: contains the main sources of information about the index.

The template also specifies the differences between the KB and the Catalogue. Initially, the KB was indeed meant to be a strictly internal file to collect any information, although sometimes in a synthetic way. In that sense, the KB should contain any potentially useful information; The Catalogue, instead, was meant to be the public expression of the KB provided to the publishers. The Catalogue therefore should contain clearer and fully useful information.

For these reasons, although minimal, some differences do exist between the KB and the Catalogue templates:

- Data collected (not in Catalogue): although the difference between indexes collecting data and those collecting metadata can be important for publishers, the difference does not always appear clearly from the indexes documentation and cannot be specified for each of them;
- Target provider type (not in Catalogue): this field is an interpretation of the skills or expertise required to upload data into an index; while the information could be useful, it is uneasy to establish with enough accuracy to record it in the Catalogue;

- Editorial minimum requirements (extended in Catalogue): while the KB records this information in a very synthetic way, the Catalogue presents it more extensively;
- Information about the sources (website, blogs, etc.): these are not reproduced in the Catalogue as they essentially constitute a way for the KB managers to check the information.

However, it has been finally decided by the task members to make public the KB itself, alongside with the Catalogue. Therefore, the public version of the KB and the Catalogue should be as aligned as possible, offering only a difference in terms of display and readability. In addition, the maintenance of the KB and the Catalogue would be better ensured thanks to this closer alignment. This is why it is planned to use the last period of the project to work on the complete alignment of the KB and of the Catalogue templates.

3.2.2 Controlled vocabularies

Although the KB template does not use authority files for its content, it uses custom controlled vocabularies that are useful for those in charge of populating the KB.

The first one concerns the indexing service types, and is as follows:

Service types	Examples
Automated aggregator with submission	Bielefeld Academic Search Engine (BASE), GoTriple, Open Access Infrastructure for Research in Europe (OpenAIRE)
Fully automated aggregator	Connecting Repositories (CORE), Gscholar, OpenAlex, Semantic Scholar
Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) Registration agency	Crossref, Datacite
Selective bibliographic and bibliometric index	Scopus, Web Of Science
Selective bibliographic index and full text repository	Central and Eastern European Online Library (CEEOL)
Selective bibliographic index	Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ), Ebsco, ERIH PLUS, PubMed

Table 2: Controlled vocabulary for index types

The KB also uses a list of controlled terms for missing and uncertain information:

None	The index doesn't ask for that kind of information
Not communicated	The information is not accessible to us but probably exists

Table 3: Controlled vocabulary for missing information

3.3 Index candidates list

The potential new entries for the KB are listed as candidates in a dedicated file and their priority level is rated by the task's partners. The rating criteria are simple: 1 for "Very relevant", 2 for "Maybe useful", 3 for "Not relevant".

	A	B	C	D	E	F
1	Add new candidates in column A		Votes from	add your name in the row below if you want		
2	Candidate	URL				
3	EZB	https://ezb.ur.de/	2	2	2	2
4	Latindex 2.0	https://latindex.org/latindex	1	1	1	1
5	Redalyc	https://www.redalyc.org/	1	1	1	1
6	ROAD	https://road.issn.org/	2	1	1	1
7	WorldCat	https://search.worldcat.org/	2	3	2	1
8	Christin	https://app.cristin.no/	2	1	3	3
9	CoKI	https://open.coki.ac/	3	3	3	3
10	Europe PMC	https://europepmc.org/	3	3	3	3
11	Finna	https://finna.fi/?lng=en-gb	1	1	1	1
12	HAL	https://hal.science/	1	1	1	1
13	HRČAK	https://hrcak.srce.hr	1	1	1	1
14	Melinda	https://melinda.kansallisk	1	2	2	2
15	MIAR	https://miar.ub.edu/	2	1	2	2
16	RePec	http://repec.org/	2	2	3	3
17	Lens	https://www.lens.org/	1	2	2	2
18						

Figure 5: Candidates list for the KB and their priority ratings

	A	B	C	D	E	F
1	1	Very relevant	Major index, for size, usage, and relevant for publishers			
2	2	Maybe useful	Useful index, but not directly under the responsibility of publishers			
3	3	Not relevant	Not real index, services useful for publishers, not for publications indexing			
4						

Figure 6: Value and criteria for the candidates' ratings

3.4 Methodology for expanding and updating the KB

As a summary of the previous sections, here is the workflow for creating a new entry in the KB:

- Selection of the new entry through the “candidates list” file;
- Creation of a new line for the selected index in the monitoring tab in “KB FOLLOW UP” file;
- Indicating the primary author responsible for gathering the information and completing the other descriptive fields of the monitoring tab;
- Creation in “KB FOLLOW UP” of a new dedicated tab for the selected entry, copy-pasting the KB template into the new tab;
- Filling in the template with the required information, following the guidelines;
- Specifying, where necessary, the provenance of the information in the “SOURCE” column of the KB template;
- First review by a person different than the primary author, comments or suggestions should be added to the “NOTES” column of the template;
- Comments and suggestions in the “NOTES” column are processed to produce the final content of the entry, addressed comments are deleted;
- Once the entry fields are all validated by the person in charge of the KB, the entry is copy-pasted into the “KB VALIDATED” file;
- After this step, the process of creating the Catalogue entry begins, with the GitHub URLs reported in both “KB FOLLOW-UP” and “KB VALIDATED” once they are ready.

Note that this workflow was followed during the CRAFT-OA project and within the related task. It can and should be adapted where necessary, changing the contributors' role and identity.

4 CATALOGUE ENTRY GENERATION

4.1 Entry model for GitHub repository

To facilitate easy reading by the end user and the conversion into Markdown, a specific Google Docs template has been created⁴. With limited reorganization of the sections of the KB, the template puts the information into tables and gives more space for detailed requirements.

4.2 Creation of a text file from the KB

The first step in creating an entry on GitHub requires producing a Markdown document. The process is pretty straightforward from Google Drive⁵.

- The information contained in the KB is copy-pasted into a .gdoc document and then converted directly into a Markdown document. The .gdoc file follows the template described above that already contains the styles (e.g. for titles) that Markdown will interpret.
- Once the Markdown document is created and correctly formatted, it is uploaded to the GitHub repository. For this step, a private GitHub repository is used in order to make final cleaning⁶.
- This private repository is then copied to the official OPERAS GitHub space as a public repository.

4.3 KB/Catalogue alignment checking

This framework produces three distinct outputs (the internal KB, the public KB, and the Catalogue) and ensures perfect alignment between them. An internal document has been set up to that end, listing the main points of attention and the preferable processes to update the three outputs consistently.

⁴ Available in Annexe 2.

⁵ The instructions to follow are described in a file accessible only to the project's partners: https://docs.google.com/document/d/1U4JeqSIOEvOLUJYgj70HrRm-Hpn_b4IkQdQ8aY3DFlg/edit?tab=t.0.

⁶ Here is the URL of the private GitHub repository: <https://github.com/agCleo/craft-oa-SchollIndexes-doc/tree/main>.

5 ACCESS POINTS TO THE KB AND THE CATALOGUE

The KB and the Catalogue are available in different formats and through different services (Google Drive and GitHub). The public version of the KB is also stored on Zenodo. In addition, some files are accessible from various tools including links to them. This section lists all the possible ways to access these components of the *Guide to Scholarly Indexes*.

5.1 Index search matrix

After some internal discussions and a public presentation of the preliminary outputs, the task members decided to develop a tool not initially planned in the Description of Action (DoA). The tool's purpose is to facilitate a pre-selection of the indexes rather than only providing the full list of index entries. The tool is based on a file named "IndexCatalogueMatrix"⁷, which describes all the indexes according to a set of criteria. These criteria only partially reproduce the fields of the KB and Catalogue. While in the KB and Catalogue the primary perspective is the one of the index actual service, in the Matrix the primary perspective is the one of a single publisher.

The Matrix identifies the following blocks of criteria, for a total of 30 criteria:

- Access types
- Scope of the index
- Evaluation process
- Data collection process
- Index available contents
- Metrics provided
- Search features
- Dissemination and reuse features

⁷ The file is internally available at: https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/17l6X3P8lynO4k-lq4gJ7uBvBEIvoZ_yFFx37tyxd8x0/edit?gid=1988175915#gid=1988175915

Index	Data collection					Index content		
	Automated retrieving	Automated retrieving after journal's submission	Manual entry by the content provider	Extraction of metadata from PDF	Collection from other indexes	Full text available	Link to the full text	Bibliographic metadata
BASE	X	X			X		X	X
CEEOL			X			X	X	X
CORE	X	X			X	X	X	X
Crossref		X	X				X	X
Datacite		X	X				X	X
Dimensions	X				X		X	X
DOAJ		X	X				X	X
EBSCO		X				X	X	X
ERIH PLUS			X				X	X
Google Scholar	X			X	X		X	X
GoTriple	X	X			X		X	X
Latindex			X			X	X	X
OpenAIRE	X	X		X	X		X	X

Figure 7: Extract from the Index Matrix showing some of the criteria

To make the Matrix more usable, a tool based on Hypertext Preprocessor/ Hypertext Markup Language (PHP/HTML) has been developed. It allows automated selection and display of the indexes selected according to these criteria.

Selection Panel

Access ^

Free for the publisher

Free for the end_user

Scope v

Evaluation ^

Data collection v

Index content ^

Full text available

Link to the full text

Bibliographic metadata

#	Name	Service type	Github page	Index website
1	BASE	Automated aggregator with submission	BASE Github Page	BASE Index website
2	CEEOL	Selective bibliographic index and full text repository	CEEOL Github Page	CEEOL Index website
3	CORE	Fully automated aggregator	CORE Github Page	CORE Index website
4	DOAJ	Selective bibliographic index	DOAJ Github Page	DOAJ Index website
5	EBSCO	Selective bibliographic index	EBSCO Github Page	EBSCO Index website
6	ERIH-PLUS	Selective bibliographic index	ERIH-PLUS Github Page	ERIH-PLUS Index website
7	Google Scholar	Fully automated aggregator	Google Scholar Github Page	Google Scholar Index website
8	OpenAlex	Fully automated aggregator	OpenAlex Github Page	OpenAlex Index website
9	PubMed	Selective bibliographic index	PubMed Github Page	PubMed Index website
10	Scopus	Selective bibliographic and bibliometric indexes	Scopus Github Page	Scopus Index website
11	Web of Science (WoS)	Selective bibliographic and bibliometric indexes	Web of Science (WoS) Github Page	Web of Science (WoS) Index website

Figure 8: Screenshot from the Index Search Matrix with the criteria selection panel and the results tab

The tool is fully operational and can be considered a valid proof-of-concept. It is currently stored on a local server only, but the objective is to make it accessible to the public. While first tests to make the tool publicly accessible can happen during the CRAFT-OA timespan, its long-term hosting and maintenance will be included in the sustainability plan described below.

5.2 KB public file (spreadsheet)

As mentioned above, the KB is publicly available in its validated form⁸. The validated KB contains only those entries that have been fully reviewed, without all the monitoring information. A draft version of the file is also published on Zenodo: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15600155>.

5.3 Catalogue public files (GitHub repository)

The Catalogue is a public GitHub repository⁹ containing all the validated entries of the KB. It is a copy of the internal GitHub repository.

Figure 9: Catalogue landing page on GitHub

⁸

https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1N_tpqMbldbxinkOyhzT9xtKIK5wpf82AFPrV5VH7IFA/edit?gid=571401641#gid=571401641

⁹ The Catalogue is available at: <https://github.com/operas-eu/craft-oa-SchollIndexes-doc/tree/main>.

5.4 DISCO OJS plugin

The CRAFT-OA project developed an OJS plugin called Discovery Companion (abbreviated as DISCO)¹⁰. Depending on the requirements of each index, the plugin allows users to check journals' compliance, either automatically or manually. The plugin also links to the Catalogue to provide publishers access to the more detailed information.

5.5 EDCH environment

Links to the KB and Catalogue should also be part of the EDCH¹¹ developed within the Developing Institutional Open Access Publishing Models to Advance Scholarly Communication (DIAMAS) sibling project. At a minimum, URLs for the KB and Catalogue public files will be included in the "Living Handbook" that is established by CRAFT-OA and will be part of the EDCH. However, the concrete integration of the *Guide to Scholarly Indexes* still has to be discussed and planned with the EDCH Executive Committee.

¹⁰ The plugin is available at: <https://github.com/munipress/disco/tree/ojs-3-2-0>.

¹¹ EDCH website available at: <https://diamas.org/>

6 NEXT STEPS AND PROSPECTS

6.1 Feedback and community enrichment

6.1.1 GitHub issues tracking

One of the easiest ways to collect feedback on the KB and Catalogue is to use the built-in issues tracking feature of GitHub. The feature could be used to report mistakes in the Catalogue, inform about updates, and potentially suggest new indexes to add. However, the feature requires users to have a GitHub account, which greatly limits the possibility of feedback.

6.1.2 EDCH forum

Another potential way, probably more accessible to all types of users, is the EDCH forum¹². The forum has been created in the context of the DIAMAS project and it can contain a topic dedicated to the KB and Catalogue. Besides questions and suggestions from the user community, the forum could also be a place for the indexes to provide information about important updates to their services.

6.2 Sustainability plans and options

During the course of the CRAFT-OA project, the T5.1 outputs became a KER, KER 6, which implies a closer consideration for their sustainability after the end of the project. KER 6 refers to all the outputs produced within T5.1, and primarily the public ones (i.e. the public KB, the public Catalogue, and the Index Search Matrix).

At the time of writing, many aspects allowing for the mid- to long-term sustainability and validity of these outputs depend on the EDCH ecosystem, which is still partly in progress. Therefore, the plans and options for sustainability remain provisional.

6.2.1 EDCH context

The EDCH is composed of various elements that we will not list here exhaustively, only to mention the ones that are of direct interest for the sustainability of KER 6. Besides the Executive Committee for the general management, the EDCH will also rely on Task Forces (TF)¹³, including a Tools and Technologies TF, where the KER 6 updates, maintenance and

¹² Available at: <https://forum.diamas.org/>.

¹³ <https://diamas.org/task-forces>

hosting could be addressed. Furthermore, the Tools and Technologies TF could be the right space to define the organisation of community engagement.

The EDCH also includes a platform that contains either original content on dedicated web pages or external content that is either standalone applications or links to specific files. In particular, the “Living Handbook” developed within CRAFT-OA work package (WP) 7, currently listing the project's outputs, should be integrated and further extended into the EDCH platform. While the KER 6 outputs are currently publicly available on specific services (see above), they could also be linked from the EDCH ecosystem, namely either directly from the platform or the “Living Handbook”.

The choice between the two options depends on which part of KER 6 is more appropriately displayed in each one. On one hand, the Index Search Matrix requires a dedicated hosting solution: it can therefore be listed in the “Living Handbook”. On the other hand, the feedback collection through the GitHub issues tracking has limitations, as seen above, and this could justify creating a dedicated webpage for the KER 6, which would include a feedback button or even a feedback form.

Given the current state of development of both the platform and the “Living Handbook” at the time of writing, their role in the sustainability of KER 6 will be clarified in the coming months.

6.2.2 Maintenance requirements

6.2.2.1 CONTENT UPDATING

At the time of writing, the KB and the Catalogue describe 20 indexes, which represent the most used and known databases for academic publications (whether open access or not). It is not expected that the rate of expansion of the KB will be very high (likely to be less than 10 per year). Indeed, the objective is rather to have accurate and extensive documentation on selected indexes, rather than an exhaustive coverage of all academic publications indexes. The process of information collection and verification is somewhat complex and demanding. For sustainability purposes, it is this aspect, rather than the number of indexes described, that must be taken into account. The current KB was achieved with a project and through collaboration between the Task Leader and the task's members. After the end of the project, another maintenance workflow has to be imagined.

As noted above, this document provides a framework to be used by persons who did not participate in the CRAFT-OA project. Nevertheless, the roles and the workflow have to be re-defined. It is planned that the verification and final validation of the new entries, as well as the updates of the former ones, will be the responsibility of the KER 6 owner. At this stage, it is envisioned that the KER 6 owner will be the former Task Leader, i.e. Aix-Marseille Université (AMU)-OpenEdition. However, to ensure better quality, the first step of information collection could be started by others: either from members of the Tools and Technologies TF, or from members of AMU-OpenEdition who were not part of the CRAFT-OA project. The

planning for regular updates (minor and major ones) could also be established through that instance.

6.2.2.2 ACCESS SUPPORT

The support required to maintain access to the outputs depends directly on the choice to be made in the following months. The public links to the KB and the Catalogue are of no concern, as they rely on stable services (Google Drive, GitHub, and Zenodo). For long-term persistence purposes, all stable files will also be deposited on Zenodo.

Questions will arise however, firstly in the context of the EDCH platform and secondly in the case of the Index Search Matrix.

Access to the KB and Catalogue from within the EDCH environment will be slightly different in the case of a dedicated webpage or in the case of integration into the "Living Handbook". Besides managing the hyperlinks, both options may require additional communications to end users to clarify the goal of KER 6 and its role within the EDCH environment. Nevertheless, the adjustments needed in both cases should remain minimal.

The case of the Index Search Matrix is a bit more complex. While adding benefit to KER 6, the tool is not a core result of the work and was not planned. Therefore its maintenance and support still have to be clarified. As a standalone application, the tool requires hosting on existing servers and probably some ongoing maintenance to fulfill both security requirements and maintain the quality of the source code. While these aspects can be discussed within the Tools and Technologies TF, the final decision for hosting and upgrading will come from the organization that accepts to take it over. Since the tool is limited in terms of volume and Central Processing Unit (CPU) consumption, the primary discussion should focus on the distribution of responsibility rather than technical aspects.

6.2.2.3 FEEDBACK MANAGEMENT

Besides the contributions from the KER 6 owner and the Tools and Technologies TF, the DOA community is also expected to further enrich and improve the description of the indexes. While the objective is not to ask the community to conduct the information collection process, it is possible to envision community feedback about potential mistakes or updates. For that purpose, the aforementioned EDCH forum seems to be the best solution. The management of these kinds of updates is linked to the question of roles mentioned above and the responsibility for the final validation of the updates. The management of such minor updates should not be an issue. However, as the EDCH forum has just been launched and the KER 6 outputs haven't been published yet, feedback management is not fully defined yet.

6.2.3 Sustainability needs

6.2.3.1 POTENTIAL NEW DEVELOPMENTS

The KB and Catalogue are documents that are ready to be shared with the public. However, they can be improved and better adapted to the end-users' needs.

The KB contains mostly raw data, and the Catalogue uses GitHub, a service that not all DOA Publishers are familiar with. Therefore, besides the Index Search Matrix, which already represents easier access to the outputs, it is possible to envision other forms of communication. The KB can be used as primary data to build detailed step-by-step documentation containing more explicit and extensive information. This last potential development could be part of the EDCH development planned over the next few years.

6.2.3.2 ESTIMATED NEED FOR SUSTAINABILITY

The identified needs for the sustainability of the *Guide to Scholarly Indexes* correspond to the following activities:

- KB updates: this includes information collection and updates, as well as propagation of the updates to all the files;
- Index Search Matrix hosting and upgrading: this includes the upgrade of the Index Search Matrix, especially in terms of security and stability, as well as its integration on a server;
- New documentation material: this refers to the development of step-by-step documentation material from the KB;
- Overall management and communication: this includes management by the organisation or body responsible for KER 6 and all communication-related activities (presentations, conferences, etc.).

A very rough guess would imagine a global effort of 6 months Full Time Equivalent (FTE) over a year.

7 REFERENCES

Gingold, A., & Cuel-Oller, N. (2024). CRAFT-OA Deliverable 5.1 Scalable and Adjustable Documentation of How to Understand the Aggregators' Technical Requirements (Draft). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12634606>

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10 ANNEX

10.1 KB entry template

	Guidelines
Summary	A brief description in 3 or 4 lines of the index, its main characteristics and features
SERVICE DESCRIPTION	
Name	Name of the index (Full name and abbreviation if needed) ex: Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ)
Website	Index home page URL (or specific URL to the index webpage)
Owner	Name of the company or institution that owns the index
Owner type	Type of the organization owning the index (Non-profit organization, Public research organization, Non-profit Partnership, Private company)
Owner country	Country where the index's owner is located
Launch year	Launch year of the index (may be distinct from index home website)
Scope	Index specific scope (scientific, geographic, access type, etc.)
Access for index users	Conditions under which the users can access the service (free, subscription fee, etc.)
Access for data providers	Conditions under which the providers can have their objects recorded in the index (closed, open, registration required, etc.)
Number of indexed items	Number of resources indexed (the number includes all the items, therefore items' type can vary and include articles, journals, publications, etc.)
Documentation: general	URL of documentation about the service (e.g. FAQ, features, accessibility, etc.)
Documentation: technical	URL of documentation about the data collection process (e.g. submission manual, metadata model, aggregation process, etc.)
Application form for providers	Direct URL of the application form for joining the index (if applicable)
SERVICE PROVISION	
Service type	Service typology created within CRAFT-OA

Content type	All the types of resources indexed (articles, journals, datasets etc.)
Content language	Language of the indexed resources
Content geographical provenance	Countries of the indexed resources
Indexing level for publications	Level of publication handled by the index (journals and/or articles)
Full text	Full text management (displayed, linked, or absent)
Index sources	Sources from which the index collects data (journals themselves, another index, databases, aggregators, etc.)
Data collected	NOT IN CATALOGUE Contents and/or metadata
Supported standard	Standards for metadata and contents accepted or generated by the index (examples: Dublin Core metadata standard, PDF, etc.)
User support	NOT IN CATALOGUE User support dedicated service
Contact address for providers	Email or contact form used to contact the index
Bibliodiversity support	A brief description of the index diversity and eventual restrictions in terms of language, scientific area, geographical provenance or registration fees
Additional services	A URL and a brief description of other tools connected with the index (API, other aggregators, data visualization tools, etc.)
INCLUSION PROCESS	
Joining options	Detailed procedure the journal needs to follow to join the index (if registration, completion of an online form, or journal evaluation is needed, etc.)
Data collection process	Detailed procedure the index will follow to collect metadata from the journal (manual or automatic collection)
Target provider type	NOT IN CATALOGUE Profile and related skills necessary to submit journal information (publishers, repository manager, etc.)
MINIMUM REQUIREMENTS	

Editorial	EXTENDED IN CATALOGUE A list of main editorial requirements the journal needs to apply to be part of the index (some of the subcategories mentioned below can be suppressed if the index doesn't have such requirements)
Data file format	A list of the accepted formats for the publications (e.g., HTML, PDF)
Metadata standard	List of standards that the metadata should follow (e.g., Dublin Core...). In this section, the requirements are mandatory unlike the first one in the supported standard section.
Metadata file format	A list of the accepted formats for metadata files (e.g. XML, JSON)
Minimum metadata	List of the metadata mandatory fields
ADDITIONAL CRITERIA	
Editorial additional specifications	Optional editorial requirements (these may be checked by the index, but are not blocking)
Recommended metadata	Recommended metadata requirements
Optional metadata	Optional metadata requirements
Other requirements	Other technical specifications fields
SEO/UX requirements	List of additional criteria required by the index to improve user experience and search engine optimization
INFORMATION SOURCES	NOT IN CATALOGUE
Wikipedia	NOT IN CATALOGUE
Index web pages	NOT IN CATALOGUE
Index news page	NOT IN CATALOGUE

10.2 Catalogue entry template

General Information

Name	
Website	
Owner	
Owner type	
Owner country	
Launch year	
Scope	
Number of items	
Access for index users	
Access for index data providers	
Documentation	
Application form for providers	

Content and Service

Service type	
Content type	
Content language	
Content geographical provenance	
Indexing level for publications	
Full text	
Index sources	
Supported standards	
Contact address for providers	

Bibliodiversity support	
--------------------------------	--

Additional services

Requirements for Academic Publications

Joining Process

Data Collection Process

Minimum Requirements

Editorial minimum requirements

Journal and publishing history

Editorial board

Publishing policy

Copyright

Technical minimum requirements

Metadata standard

Data file format

Metadata file format

Metadata mandatory fields

Additional Criteria

(Same categories as minimum requirements)

Editorial additional specifications

Technical additional specifications

Metadata recommended fields

Metadata optional fields

Other technical specifications

SEO/UX requirements

